

THE CONCEPT OF FREEDOM IN G. G. BYRON'S "CHILDE HAROLD'S PILGRIMAGE"

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Abstract

The creative activities of the great English poet George Gordon Byron entered the history of world literature as an outstanding artistic phenomenon associated with the era of romanticism, which arose in Western Europe at the end of the 18th – beginning of the 19th century. An ardent defender of the national movement for freedom, an exposé of tyranny and the policy of invading warriors, Byron became one of the leading figures of the progressive trend in romanticism for his struggle for liberty. The innovative spirit of Byron's poetry, his artistic method of a new type of romance was picked up and developed by subsequent generations of poets and writers of various national literatures. Many of Byron's works sound like a revolutionary call to struggle, he reveals the injustice of the ruling class, calls on the people to fight for freedom. Among them, the poems "Childe Harold's Pilgrimage", "Manfred", "Giaur", "Corsair", "Prisoner of Chillon" and others are the most significant.

Key words: the concept of freedom, pilgrimage, romanticism, revolutionary poetry, liberty movement.

Romantic poets possessed a unique ability to express their own point of view in their works, advocating freedom of self-expression. In their work, in their characters, romantic poets reflected themselves, their aspirations, their feelings, their worldview, their own destiny. This feature was most vividly embodied in the works of Byron.

Byron always demanded truthfulness in the depiction of phenomena. In his work, the noble poet touched upon psychological and social issues. He was not afraid to confront the society, which celebrated victory without understanding the real state of

affairs. The poet saw only the replacement of one tyrant by another and resolutely declared this. Such sentiments secured Byron the fate of an exile, the fate of a destitute, the same as the heroes of his works. But, again and again, he continued to call people to fight. Lord Byron refused to recognize the defeat of man in the face of cruel fate, called for resistance, for action.

Until the end of his life, Byron remained a true patriot of England. With all his creativity, as an active fighter for freedom, he proved the need to fight against violence and evil. And his literary heritage has not lost its relevance and freshness in the following years. His progressive ideas enriched world poetry, and *"his traditions were continued and developed by poets of subsequent generations"* (Horova, 2014, p. 93).

Up to nowadays, Byron's poetry, filled with the spirit of freedom and justice, rich in deep thoughts, developing noble feelings, excites people's minds, leading them along the path of life. The poet became a model of honesty and independence for his readers.

All the poetry of George Byron, the great English poet, is permeated by the pathos of irreconcilable protest, historical optimism and proclamation of freedom, which were fueled by the national liberation movements breaking out all over Europe. And Byron, a poet and a citizen, *"a witness and a participant in the historical process, once dreamed of a career as an orator, a political figure"* (Solrun, 2012, p. 17).

"Childe Harold's Pilgrimage" is a narrative poem that stands as one of the most idiosyncratic and enduring of Romantic works emphasizing the importance of travel to the development and growth of the self in a way that seems strikingly modern. The first section, or canto, of the poem was published in 1812, the final one in 1818. Spanning four cantos, the poem follows the travels of Childe Harold, a dissipated and world-weary young man who travels the world seeking for something that even he isn't quite able to articulate. Harold has a licentious and troubling, although vague, past, and according to Byron's narration, is ultimately running from an unnamed trauma.

G. Byron's lyric-epic poem "Childe Harold's Pilgrimage" is distinguished by the pathos of love of freedom, heroism, and citizenship. The poet does not lose faith in the rebirth of freedom, admiring the splendor of nature, sympathizing with enslaved Greece, observing the courage of the Spaniards, observing the defiance of Albania. The

energy of the poem is aimed at reviving the revolutionary spirit. Byron called for it in every line of his work.

At some point, Byron was confused by conflicting feelings, horror, he spoke about the inevitable death of a person before the onslaught of brute force:

*Full swiftly Harold wends his lonely way
Where proud Sevilla triumphs unsubdued:
Yet is she free – the spoiler's wished-for prey!
Soon, soon shall conquest's fiery foot intrude,
Blackening her lovely domes with traces rude.
Inevitable hour! against fate to strive,
Where desolation plants her famished brood,
Is vain, or Ilion, Tyre might yet survive,
And virtue vanquish all, and murder cease to thrive” (Byron, 2004).*

“A person”, Byron claims, “is not a passive object. What is truly human lies precisely in the ability and desire to defend one's freedom and one's principles before this formidable and hostile force” (Olsen, 2010, p. 112).

Both the author of the poem and his hero find this truth as a result of enriching their life experience and intense ideological searches. Byron assigns an active role in history to people who fight against the injustices of this world, people who are able to give their lives for their beliefs and ideals. However, the role assigned to man in Byron's poem *Childe Harold's Pilgrimage* is not only a heroic role, but also a profoundly tragic role. A person is doomed to an endless struggle, which sometimes leads to death, but not to the breaking of heroic resistance, the cancellation of views. The democratic tendencies of the poem are revealed in Byron's desire to show that the people are the driving force of the history.

Byron's work “*Childe Harold's Pilgrimage*” brought the poet world fame, becoming a masterpiece of romanticism. It was written as a result of a trip to Europe in 1812. The diary notes created by Byron during the trip became the basis of *Childe Harold's Pilgrimage*. The countries visited by Harold are depicted in bright colors, he

describes “*the local flavor of European countries, the way of life and customs of different people*” (Osborne, 2001, p. 57).

But with all the abundance and variety of shades, the picture created by Byron has an internal integrity. In Byron's image, each individual country: Albania, Spain, Greece – has its own special individual face, while being a part of a single inseparable whole. The tragic consequences of the revolution and the establishment of tyranny are a common theme of the work. “Childe Harold’s Pilgrimage” shows the process of enslaving the peoples of Europe, establishing new forms of power.

All parts of the poem are saturated with historical and philosophical thoughts in connection with the consequences of the French Revolution. Byron's writing style also changes: simplification of linguistic units, bolder images, pronounced subjectivism carry an even greater departure from classical literary traditions.

The Spanish people were the first to give a worthy rebuff to Napoleon. The images of the liberating soldiers are colorful, but believable. The poet is indignant about the invasion of soldiers on peaceful lands, when shepherds and farmers have to leave their work and go to war to die, kill or mutilate their souls. Byron speaks with disgust about violence, bloodshed:

*Oh, lovely Spain! renowned, romantic land!
Where is that standard which Pelagio bore,
When Cava’s traitor-sire first called the band
That dyed thy mountain streams with Gothic gore* (Byron, 2004).

Byron does not want to see destitute people. He not only feels sorry for them, but also calls for a fight:

*O’er vales that teem with fruits, romantic hills,
(Oh, that such hills upheld a freeborn race!
Poor, paltry slaves! yet born midst noblest scenes
Why, Nature, waste thy wonders on such men?
Awake, ye sons of Spain! awake! advance!* (Byron, 2004).

The main part of the second song is devoted to Harold's stay in Greece and Albania. Albania is a country of mighty warriors who warmly welcome travelers:

Fierce are Albania's children, yet they lack

Not virtues, were those virtues more mature.

Where is the foe that ever saw their back?

Who can so well the toil of war endure? (Byron, 2004)

The third part of "Pilgrimage" is the most poignant. Here Byron condemns false patriotic literature, he closely follows the development of events in the world, especially in England, expressing his indignation in the sharp lines of his work. However, he does not consider the revolution to be an empty affair, he respects and glorifies it.

The fourth part of the poem is devoted to Italy. Italy appears in front of Harold in the festive splendor of nature and works of art, but at the same time in bloody tears. The deprivations of the Italian people were caused by the tyranny of the Austrian conquerors. The monarchs who rule over the state introduce inquisitional methods of combatting dissidents. The greatness of Italian cities has been replaced by devastation, there are more and more vagrants and beggar children on the streets.

Lord George Byron is a sincere revolutionary fighter. In his works, imbued with civil pathos, especially in the lyric-epic poem "Childe Harold's Pilgrimage", there is an ardent call to fight for freedom, rights, fight against the injustices of a cruel world. Having created a truly great poem about war and peace, the poet introduced an innovative work into the world of literature that does not lose its relevance even today.

Byron's poem raises important questions of freedom, morality, ecology, politics, and social life in our lives. Why do people kill their own kind? Why are innocent children, elderly people and women dying? Why are the riches of nature destroyed, and what will all this ultimately lead to? Why should people who live peacefully on earth suffer because of the wrong policies of other people who only want wealth?

By answering these questions, Byron arouses the anger of the ruling circles of England at that time. The one who speaks the truth, who conveys to the consciousness of other people the true state of affairs, is subject to criticism and expulsion from the country. But even outside his homeland, the author of "Pilgrimage" calls for a revolution. He does not give up his beliefs for a single moment, even at the cost of his

own life as a wanderer. Living in different countries, Byron draws the attention of readers to the political and social problems of the people of Europe.

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